

Fatigue life extension of welded steel structures **Summary of *LifeExt* research projects conducted 2017 -2024**

Hassan Al-Karawi^a, Joakim Hedegård^b, Mohammad Al-Emrani^c

^aCOWI Sweden, hsak@cowi.com

^b Swerim AB, joakim.hedegard@swerim.se

^c Chalmers University of Technology mohammad.alemrani@chalmers.se

ABSTRACT

Fatigue is a vital design consideration in several steel structures that are subjected to fluctuating loading such as bridges, ships, cranes, and aircraft. In addition, many of these structures have reached their design life, and they should be either replaced or strengthened. In *LifeExt* project, the potential of using two post-weld treatment methods for prolonging the fatigue lives of existing structures is investigated. The research conducted includes experimental and numerical investigations. The results show a great potential of using High-Frequency Mechanical Impact (HFMI) treatment and Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) remelting for the purpose of extending the service life of existing structures. Combining both methods is found to give an increased efficiency.

Keywords: HFMI treatment, TIG remelting, Fatigue, Life Extension, Crack

1 INTRODUCTION

Fatigue is a degradation phenomenon that takes place in metallic structures when they are subjected to cyclic loading. Fatigue is a progressive process where fatigue damage accumulates through the service life of the structure. Therefore, it is vital to take fatigue into consideration in the design of new metallic components prone to cyclic loading, not least when this component is welded. Welds are more prone to fatigue because of several reasons, such as local flaws emerging in and in the vicinity of the weldment and residual stresses that usually prevail the weld toe region after cooling down. Therefore, welded components usually exhibit weaker resistance to fatigue loading than parent material which is reflected in the *Wöhler curves* used for fatigue design.

Fatigue damage is characterized by its progressiveness which implies that more damage should be expected for longer in-service lives. This represents quite a challenge for structures designed for relatively long lives such as bridges, wind turbines, ships, and cranes. Today, thousands of these structures are in-service and soon decision should be made whether they should be replaced by new ones, or if their lives can be extended, and fatigue progression retarded. The latter is a preferable option economically and environmentally as it mitigates new material consumption by making use of what already exists (1). However, a technical solution should be provided in order to claim longer life despite the existing fatigue damage that have accumulated throughout the service life of the structure.

Post weld treatment (PWT) is a term used to describe a family of methods aimed at reducing a detrimental fatigue effect by imposing local changes (2). PWT works on mildening or counteracting the unwanted effects of welding such as tensile residual stresses or stress

concentrations. One example of PWT is re-welding to milden the transition of the weld to its neighboring plates. However, this can generate un-wanted additional distortions due the extra heat input. Therefore, remelting the weld toe alone can be preferable as the heat -in this case- would be limited to the weld toe's vicinity (3), but this requires use of locally focused welding arc such as Tungsten Inert Gas remelting (TIG-remelting) aimed at the weld transition area (i.e. the weld toe).

Another type of PWT relies on reducing the residual stresses at the weld toes through mechanical peening of the weld transition to the welded plate (2). This is achievable using different tools such as hammer peening, pneumatic impacting, or high-frequency impact treatment. The last mentioned is believed to be the most efficient as it produces finer surfaces after treatment (2). This method is acronymed HFMI treatment (High-Frequency Mechanical Impact treatment). HFMI does not only reduce the prevailing tensile residual stresses, but it also replaces them with more beneficial compressive residual stresses. In addition, it usually increases the hardness of the toe vicinity by cold-working, and it often also smoothen the weld toe transition (2).

In the years between 2017-2024, two consecutive research projects are conducted by several Swedish research organizations, companies, and The Swedish Transport Administration (TRV). The projects, *LifeExt* and *LifeExt-2*, were aimed at investigating the potential of PWT for extending the lives of existing welded steel structures that have presumably undergone some fatigue damage during their service lives. This paper highlights important findings to pave the way for safe and reliable fatigue life extension via local post-weld treatment with TIG and HFMI.

2 METHODS

The work conducted in the *LifeExt* project commenced with a literature study on the use of the investigated methods (HFMI-treatment or TIG-remelting). The results of this study is summarized in (4). Thereafter, experimental work was performed, comprising of fatigue testing before and after life-extension, and auxiliary investigations including residual stress measurements, weld topography scanning, hardness testing, and macro- and metallographic examinations. Table 1 shows an overview of the conducted investigations.

In addition to the experimental research listed above, several numerical models were created to model the treatment. As TIG remelting enables crack removal in the fusion zone, the life prediction models should be crack-free. However, HFMI treatment does not cause crack removal which implies that the used models should include these cracks. Table 2 summarizes the models used in the *lifeExt* projects.

In addition to the experimental investigations, a literature study was carried out to collect relevant fatigue test results for comparisons. This includes cracked or pre-fatigued specimens treated by either HFMI treatment or TIG remelting as a resemblance of a treated existing structure. In addition, another data pool was collected for specimens tested in corrosive medium and treated by HFMI. This also necessitated collecting data for specimens tested in normal conditions (with no pre-fatigue damage or corrosion) More information about the collected data is given in (4,5).

Table 1. Experimental investigations conducted in *LifeExt* projects.

Experiment	Description	Illustration	Relevant publications
Fatigue testing	Axial fatigue testing of steel specimens under different loading conditions in order to investigate the fatigue resistance prior to and after a PWT-treatment. The tested specimens commented here consisted of steel plates with welded transverse stiffeners.		(3,6)
Crack detection	Several identical specimens being fatigue tested to specific level to generate fatigue cracking. The depth of the crack is quantified via ultrasonic testing , and the crack depth is calibrated to strain drop measured via strain gauges .		(7)
Residual stress measurement	Hole drilling technique is employed to investigate the residual stress in the thickness direction in the weld vicinity before or after PWT-treatment.		(3,6,8)
Hardness testing	3 Kg Vicker hardness tester is used to investigate the effect of treatment on the local hardness.		(3,6,8)
Laser scanning	Scanning the local geometry of the weld toe using the scanner (<i>Winteria System</i>) to investigate the change in weld toe radius and perform other measurements.		(3,6)
Microscopy and metallographic examinations	Studying the micro-structure in the vicinity of the weld toe after treatment and the fatigue crack behavior before and after treatment.		(3,6,8)

Table 2. Modelling in *LifeExt* projects.

Description	Governing equations	publication
A simplified model based on Basquin equation to explain the outstanding fatigue strength of TIG treated specimens by incorporating the several changes induced by a treatment (residual stress, local geometry, hardness and distortions). The model is verified with existing experimental results.	$\Delta\sigma_l = k_t \Delta\sigma_g$ $\Delta\sigma_{m,l} = k_t \Delta\sigma_{m,g}$ $\Delta\sigma_{m,tot} = \Delta\sigma_{m,l} + \sigma_{RS} + \sigma_{clamp}$ $\Delta\sigma_{ar} = \frac{\Delta\sigma_l}{1 - \frac{\sigma_{m,tot}}{\sigma_{u,l}}}$	(3)
Stress intensities together with weight functions are used to construct the crack growth curves of HFMI treated detail containing cracks. The local changes are incorporated in the definition of the effective R -ratio, and Paris law is employed to construct the propagation curves. The effect of residual stress field and remaining crack size are investigated through a parametric study.	$K = \int_0^a m(x, a) \cdot \sigma(x) dx$ $R_{eff} = \frac{K_{min} + K_{RS} + K_{CS}}{K_{max} + K_{RS} + K_{CS}}$ $da = \begin{cases} C \cdot \frac{(K_{max} - K_{min})^m}{(1.5 - R_{eff})^m} dN, & K_{max} - K_{min} > K_{th} \\ 0, & \text{Otherwise} \end{cases}$	(7)
Mechanical elasto-plastic finite element model to study the crack closure and introduced compression at the crack tip. Parametric study is performed for the crack size, the impact of position and the angle of indentation.	-	(9)
Thermo mechanical elasto-plastic finite element modeling of the combined treatment (TIG remelting followed by HFMI treatment). Crack initiation and propagation models are used. Fatigue damage is calculated based on the resulted strains, and the elements are deleted when the fatigue damage reaches unity. The scanned geometry and local hardness are introduced in the model, and residual stress relaxation during cracking is considered in the model	$\frac{\sigma_{RS}}{\sigma_{RS,cycle}} = N_i^k$ $\Delta\sigma_{ar} = \frac{\Delta\sigma_{Loc}}{1 - \frac{\sigma_{u,Loc} + \sigma_{RS}}{\sigma_{u,L}}}$ $\Delta\epsilon = \frac{\Delta\sigma_{ar}}{E} + K \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta\sigma_{ar}}{E}\right)^n$ $\frac{\Delta\epsilon}{2} = \frac{\sigma_f'}{E} (2 \cdot N_f)^b + \epsilon_f' (2N_f)^c$	(10)

3 RESULTS

Since the scope of *LifeExt* is on prolonging life of existing structures, it was quite important to design a methodology of damage detection as a resemblance of existing structures that have been subjected to a percentage of fatigue damage throughout their service lives. Therefore, the specimens were equipped with several strain gauges at the weld toe. The drop of strain indicates crack growth. Therefore, the strain drop is calibrated for crack size using ultrasonic testing and destructive investigations. In addition, strain gauge positioning is selected based on elastic finite element analyses given in (7).

The results of fatigue tests conducted are presented in the Fig 1. Six series of specimens are tested. Two series served as reference including As welded and HFMI treated specimens. Three series of included specimens containing cracks 0.6-1.2 mm deep at the weld toe, and then treated afterwards using different treatment methods; (HFMI treatment, TIG remelting or TIG followed by HFMI treatment). Surprisingly, the fatigue strength was found to be relatively high even with no post-weld treatment. However, HFMI-treatment enabled a further increase in the fatigue strength. For the cracked specimens, the cracks were first created by fatigue testing to resemble existing structures as stated earlier. Then, the specimens were treated and tested to failure. No significant difference was found between pre-fatigued (i.e. with crack) and new specimens, for HFMI treatment. In other words, HFMI-treatment of pre-cracked specimens resulted in a life extension equivalent to the fatigue life of new HFMI-treated specimens. In

addition, none of the specimens failed from the weld toe after TIG remelting or combined treatment which indicates the successfulness of the treatment.

Fig. 1. R: Fatigue test results L : Tested specimens and the attached gauges to monitor crack growth

TIG remelting enables removal of shallow cracks which explains the outstanding fatigue extension that was observed in the treated specimens. However, this is conditioned by the achieving a sufficient TIG weld depth to remove the whole crack. Therefore, the TIG electrode is placed right at the weld toe and focused downwards to maximize the fusion depth. This is slightly in contradiction with the International Institute of Welding recommendations for new structures enhanced by TIG remelting, see Figure 2 below.

Fig. 2. Different positioning and arc direction of TIG electrode; different shapes of fusion zones (B results in deeper fusion)

In order to study the effect of existing damage on the efficiency of HFMI treatment and TIG remelting, fatigue test results in *LifeExt* project together with data collected from literature were analyzed using an efficiency factor called “Gain factor *G*”. *G* gives the ratio between the fatigue life of the treated specimens obtained experimentally to the characteristic fatigue life of the same treated details according to the IIW recommendations, see Figure 3. This is plotted against the number of cycles before treatment normalized to the characteristic fatigue life. The figure clearly shows that in all studied cases, the gain factor is greater than 1.0 which indicates the efficiency of both treatments despite an already existing fatigue damage.

Fig. 3. Gain factor G in fatigue lives plotted against pre-fatigue lives normalized to the characteristic lives according to IIW recommendations.

Since the studied methods are local, it is vital to examine the local changes produced by the studied processes from a material point of view. Therefore, residual stresses are measured in the thickness direction for specimens in different states. In addition, microhardness is measured in the weld toe vicinity. The results are given in Fig 4 and 5 respectively. HFMI treatment induces compressive residual stresses and hardens the weld toe vicinity. In addition, when preceded by TIG remelting, further hardening and compressive residual stresses will be induced.

Fig. 4. Measured residual stresses in different specimens before and after treatment

Fig. 5. Local hardness mapping before and after treatment

The effect of combining both treatment methods could not be studied directly because all treated specimens failed in fatigue from the base metal far from the welded regions. Therefore, the results of the conducted numerical analysis are used for comparison, see Fig 6 which shows the fatigue lives of fatigue-loaded and treated welded details in steel. Contrary to TIG-remelting, a combined treatment is quite useful in suppressing any potential crack propagation. Nonetheless, larger HFMI indentors shall be used to attain the geometry improvement made by the TIG remelting. Fig 6 shows that the combined treatment results in approximately the same improvement in toe radius as for a pure TIG remelting.

Fig. 6. Comparison of crack growth of new vs existing structures treated by TIG remelting or combined treatment with TIG+ HFMI.

Fig. 7. Local geometry improvements achieved by different post-weld treatment methods.

TIG remelting is associated with higher cost and requires more skilled labor in comparison to HFMI-treatment. Therefore, it is economic to decide when each treatment is necessary. In practice, applying HFMI-treatment after TIG-remelting should not be a problem as it is easy to operate and relatively cheap and fast. In any way, non-destructive testing (NDT) is needed to verify whether there are any surface cracks in the details to be treated before any treatment is applied on an existing structure.

One of the simplest NDT methods that can be used to reveal surface cracks in metallic structures is the use of dye penetrant testing. If the NDT is negative, HFMI-treatment can be used without toe remelting as there is no crack observed. Otherwise, similar welded detail should be

manufactured, and treated by TIG-remelting with specific parameters (i.e. treatment speed, voltage, current and heat input). Afterwards, metal inspection is needed to assess the sufficiency of the fusion depth in relation to the existing crack size. If the TIG fusion depth is larger, then TIG-remelting can be applied to the structure with these weld data.

HFMI-treatment can then be applied to put the area under compression. For other cases, when a removal or closure of the existing crack cannot be guaranteed, further investigation on TIG-HFMI treatment is needed to verify the capability of this treatment in inducing compression at both remaining internal crack tips. It is noteworthy that the NDT used must be able to detect a 2 mm crack with a high probability of crack detection (7). The flowchart in Fig 8. summarizes the mentioned procedures.

Corrosion is known to negatively affect the fatigue lives of welded structures. Therefore, a literature study was conducted to investigate this effect on HFMI treated structures. Fig 9 displays the gain factor in fatigue life plotted against the corrosion level presented as the multiplication of the concentration of the corrosive medium by the immersion time. The figure clearly indicates an adverse relation between the fatigue life and the corrosion level. However, the risk of having fatigue lives shorter than the characteristic design life of HFMI treated details, in the studied pool, does not exceed 4%. Nevertheless, it is still recommended to apply corrosion protection layer, and to remove the eventual sharp edges generated by a HFMI treatment.

More than 150 fatigue test results on corroded and HFMI-treated welded details have been collected from several research articles and analysed for both transverse welded attachment and butt-welded details. The efficiency of a HFMI treatment decreases in corroded details as the corrosion level increases. However, HFMI treatment is found to have a high potential in prolonging the fatigue life, even in circumstances of an extremely corrosive environment.

Fig. 8. Flow chart for life extension using HFMI treatment or TIG remelting

Fig. 9. Adverse relationship between the fatigue life and corrosion level

More investigations of the applicability of HFMI treatment on existing steel bridges are studied in *LifeExt2* research project. One output of this project is to provide a practical guideline for the usage of HFMI treatment including what should to be done before and after treatment to ensure good effectiveness. In fact, these guidelines apply for any steel structure with slight modifications. A summary of the guidelines is given in Fig 10. The interested readers are referred to the open final report for *LifeExt* project (11).

Fig. 10. Practical guidelines for the application of HFMI treatment on bridges

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper summarizes some of the outcomes of the first *LifeExt* projects. It has been shown here that a significant fatigue life extension is achievable using local HFMI treatment, and TIG remelting. Combining these two methods was shown to produce superior results. In this project, fatigue testing, and other experimental investigations were conducted to investigate the potential and suitable application methodology for the PWT methods for existing structures. In addition, numerical investigations were employed to study the different changes induced by treatments such as residual stresses, micro-structure, and local geometry. Practical guidelines are suggested based on the results of the conducted research, shedding the light on when and how to use either of the suggested treatment methods and the pre-work needed. Since only some (weaker) parts of a welded structure take most of a fatigue damage and this damage is very

local, life extension work can be focused to these places which will be highly cost efficient and sustainable.

A following implementation project, LifeExt2, investigates the quality assurance for the PWT methods and will test-implement PWT methods on a bridge in Sweden, make lessons learned and modify procedures and guidelines accordingly.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The projects LifeExt and *LifeExt2* are financed by the Swedish agency of innovation, *Vinnova*, *InfraSweden2030*, and the participating companies. This is gratefully acknowledged. *InfraSweden2030* is also thanked for their coaching and information activities.

REFERENCES

1. REID, Iain L. Kennedy; MILNE, David M.; CRAIG, Richard E. Steel Bridge Strengthening: a study of assessment and strengthening experience and identification of solutions. Thomas Telford, 2001.
2. MARQUIS, Gary B., et al. IIW Recommendations on high frequency mechanical impact (HFMI) treatment for improving the fatigue strength of welded joints. Springer Singapore, 2016.
3. AL-KARAWI, Hassan; UND POLACH, RU Franz von Bock; AL-EMRANI, Mohammad. Fatigue crack repair in welded structures via tungsten inert gas remelting and high frequency mechanical impact. Journal of constructional steel research, 2020, 172: 106200.
4. AL-KARAWI, Hassan; AL-EMRANI, Mohammad. The efficiency of HFMI treatment and TIG remelting for extending the fatigue life of existing welded structures. Steel construction, 2021, 14.2: 95-106.
5. AL-KARAWI, Hassan. Corrosion Effect on the Efficiency of High-Frequency Mechanical Impact Treatment in Enhancing Fatigue Strength of Welded Steel Structures. Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance, 2022, 31.11: 9151-9158.
6. AL-KARAWI, Hassan, et al. Fatigue life extension of existing welded structures via high frequency mechanical impact (HFMI) treatment. Engineering structures, 2021, 239: 112234.
7. AL-KARAWI, Hassan; VON BOCK UND POLACH, Rüdiger U. Franz; AL-EMRANI, Mohammad. Crack detection via strain measurements in fatigue testing. Strain, 2021, 57.4: e12384.
8. AL-KARAWI, Hassan. Material and residual stress improvement in S355 welded structural steel using mechanical and thermal post-weld treatment methods. Steel Construction, 2022, 15.1: 51-54.
9. Al-Karawi, H., M. Al-Emrani, and J. Hedegård. "Crack behaviour after High Frequency Mechanical Impact treatment in welded S355 structural steel." Bridge Maintenance, Safety, Management, Life-Cycle Sustainability and Innovations. CRC Press, 2021. 3113-3119.

10. *Al-Karawi, Hassan Ayad.* "Fatigue life estimation of welded structures enhanced by combined thermo-mechanical treatment methods." *Journal of Constructional Steel Research* 187 (2021): 106961.
11. *Hedegård, J and Al-Emrani, M and Edgren, M and Manai, A and Al-Karawi, H and Barsoum, Z* "LifeExt -Prolonged life for existing steel bridges -Livslängdsförlängning av befintliga stålbroar" Open report, 2020 , DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.24449.99681